

4I-GEP

Faculty of Physical Education and Sport

Charles University

This Gender Equality Plan was developed thanks to our participation in the SUPPORTER project, which supports institutions in Central and Eastern Europe in creating intersectional, innovative, inclusive, and impactful (4I) Gender Equality Plans. The project provided expert guidance, mentoring, and a focus on addressing gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

The Gender Equality Plan of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport was discussed and approved by the Dean's Board on 27.5.2025 and discussed by the Academic Senate of the Faculty on 17.6.2025.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Institutional context

Charles University has demonstrated a long-term commitment to gender equality through a structured and evolving approach. The first Gender Equality Plan (GEP) for the period 2022–2024 introduced the foundational concept and outlined key initial activities aimed at promoting equal opportunities across the institution. It established essential institutional structures such as the Ombudsperson and the Equal Opportunities Board and was primarily informed by the results of the 2021 gender audit.

Building on this groundwork, the GEP for 2025–2027 was developed in close cooperation with all 17 faculties and relevant university departments. Its preparation was based on the implementation experience of the previous plan and new data sources, including the 2024 university-wide survey on caregivers' needs. It also incorporated comprehensive evaluations of earlier activities and feedback from the Ombudsperson's Office and the Council for Equal Opportunities. A valuable contribution to the development of the new plan came from the international project SUPPORTER (Securing sports Education through innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans), which Charles University has been actively involved in. This project enabled deeper exchange of experience and best practices in promoting equality, diversity, and inclusion, and significantly influenced the structure and ambitions of the new GEP.

The 2025–2027 GEP represents a substantial advancement in scope, structure, and strategic orientation. One of its key innovations is the explicit focus on intersectionality. While the previous plan primarily addressed gender equality, the new GEP recognizes and responds to overlapping and interrelated forms of vulnerability, such as those related to age, ethnicity, health status, or socio-economic background. This shift introduces a more inclusive and comprehensive equality framework.

The plan also refines and expands the university's data collection methods. Building on the 2021 audit, it integrates new targeted research, such as the caregivers' needs survey, and establishes regular and systematic monitoring tools, including quarterly reports, annual evaluations, stakeholder consultations, and follow-up surveys to assess impact and adjust measures accordingly.

Stakeholder engagement has evolved from the establishment of institutional structures to their active and systemic involvement in equality measures. The Ombudsperson's Office, the Equal Opportunities Board, and

key university departments—such as Research, Student Affairs, and Human Resources—are now more strongly integrated into both the development and continuous implementation of the plan.

A further shift is visible in the plan’s internal structure. Unlike the previous GEP, which included general goals without distinguishing between recommended and compulsory actions, the new plan sets out 69 clearly defined measures across nine thematic areas. Each measure is linked to specific objectives, key actions, indicators, timelines, and responsible actors, fully aligning with current standards for strategic planning and European-level requirements.

Support and training services have also been significantly strengthened. Whereas the previous plan focused primarily on awareness-raising, the new GEP introduces a broad range of practical support mechanisms. These include comprehensive training programs addressing social safety, gender-based violence, and crisis intervention, as well as targeted psychological support for students, staff, and athletes.

International collaboration continues to play an important role. While previous efforts included basic cooperation and sharing of good practices, the new GEP builds on these foundations and places greater emphasis on learning from foreign institutions, adapting international examples of successful equality and inclusion initiatives to the university context.

Finally, the GEP demonstrates stronger alignment with funding strategies and relevant policy frameworks at both national and international levels. In contrast to the earlier plan, which referred only generally to potential sources of support, the new GEP identifies concrete opportunities for funding and strategic development, ensuring that equality measures are not only well-designed but also realistically implementable.

In summary, the 2025–2027 Gender Equality Plan reflects a shift from foundational activities to a comprehensive, inclusive, and well-integrated approach to equality. It builds on experience, research, stakeholder collaboration, and international exchange, particularly through the SUPPORTER project, to deliver a forward-looking and institutionally embedded strategy for the coming years.

1.2. Purpose of the Faculty’s 4I-GEP

Within the broader framework of Charles University’s institutional commitment to gender equality, the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (FTVS UK) has undertaken the development of its own Gender Equality Plan (GEP) tailored to the specific needs and realities of a sport-

oriented academic environment. This initiative reflects our ongoing efforts to translate university-wide strategic goals into meaningful, context-sensitive actions that resonate with the faculty's culture, disciplines, and community.

Our active participation in the international project SUPPORTER played a crucial role in shaping both the new university-level GEP and our faculty-specific approach. The project offered valuable feedback on the 2022–2024 GEP and facilitated close collaboration in preparing the new plan for 2025–2027. Importantly, the SUPPORTER partnership also provided FTVS UK with unique expertise and insights that are currently not available within the Czech academic landscape, where no other sport-focused faculty has yet developed a dedicated GEP. This international collaboration enabled us to contribute relevant perspectives to the university-wide plan, while also strengthening our own capacity to address gender-related challenges specific to the field of sport sciences.

Aligned with the mission, vision, and values of FTVS UK—centred on excellence, inclusivity, responsibility, and respect—the GEP supports our strategic goal of fostering a fair, equitable, and high-performing academic and professional environment. As a faculty committed to health promotion, human development, and lifelong physical activity, we view gender equality not only as a matter of rights and justice but also as essential to our educational and research excellence.

The preparation of this faculty-specific GEP was significantly enriched through the SUPPORTER project. The project's international dimension provided comparative perspectives and best practices, allowing us to place our local experience within a wider European context. This exchange has empowered us to approach gender equality with greater nuance, particularly in relation to sport education and research, and has allowed us to become an active contributor to shared European standards in this area.

Building on these foundations, the FTVS Gender Equality Plan 2025–2027 is designed to complement the strategic direction of Charles University while addressing the faculty's distinct academic and professional environment. The plan is guided by the principles of intersectionality, innovation, inclusiveness, and impact (the 4Is), which are embedded across all areas of faculty operations. Through this approach, FTVS UK aims to create a safer, more inclusive, and empowering environment for all members of its diverse community.

2. Situation Analysis and Rationale

2.1. Sports-Specific Context

The Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (FTVS UK) operates in an academic environment shaped by the dynamics of sports education. Several key factors underline the need for a faculty-specific Gender Equality Plan (GEP):

- **Power balance:** The hierarchical nature of coach–athlete relationships can intensify vulnerabilities, emphasizing the need for clear codes of conduct, transparent communication standards, and accessible reporting mechanisms to ensure safety and trust.
- **Support for equal representation:** Women remain underrepresented in sport research, leadership positions, and advanced coaching roles. This limits diversity, inclusion, and innovation in both academic and professional environments, highlighting the need for targeted support measures.
- **Intersectional Realities:** Students and staff may encounter overlapping forms of disadvantage based on gender, disability, socio-economic background, ethnicity, or age. These intersecting identities impact their access to opportunities necessitating inclusive policies and practices that reflect diverse lived experiences.
- **Psychological Wellbeing:** Individuals in sports environments face unique pressures linked to performance, competition, and constant evaluation. Accessible and tailored psychological support is crucial to fostering a healthy, balanced environment for both athletes and staff.
- **Education in Social Competencies:** Skills such as communication, teamwork, and conflict resolution are vital in sports and beyond. These competencies must be systematically integrated into educational and training programs to equip students and staff for real-life social challenges.

2.2. Initial Analysis and Institutional Learning

During 2023–2024, FTVS UK conducted an internal review to assess the state of gender equality within the faculty. This included:

- **Stakeholder Consultations:** Faculty members, students, administrative staff, and leadership were engaged through survey, workshops, and interviews. Input was also gathered from the ombudsperson and university-level equality bodies. FTVS UK worked with analyses carried out during the preparation of the university's Gender Equality Plan (GEP) as well as its subsequent update. The data

were collected through a questionnaire survey specifically targeted at students, conducted as part of the Supporter project, and subsequently analysed the results. The data from our analyses have been acknowledged by the HR department and the Deans' Board, leading to the identification of key observations.

- **Key Observations:**
 - Knowledge gaps exist in areas such as awareness on gender-based violence (GBV), bystander awareness, and available support services.
 - A strong need was identified for staff training, clearer reporting pathways, and improved representation in decision-making.
 - Intersectionality should be better reflected in training and curriculum development to address diverse needs and backgrounds. Intersectionality is taken into account through support for diverse groups of students and staff.
- **Learning through SUPPORTER:** Participation in the international SUPPORTER project significantly contributed to institutional awareness and capacity-building. Faculty members took part in:
 - Training programs focused on gender equality in sports contexts.
 - Mutual learning exchanges with international peers.
 - The development of tailored approaches to address intersectionality, GBV prevention, and gender-sensitive teaching and leadership practices.

These insights, combined with analysis of current faculty practices and feedback, confirmed the need for a dedicated faculty-level GEP.

3. Faculty-Level GEP Principles

The decision to create a dedicated GEP for FTVS UK builds on Charles University's institutional framework but addresses the distinct context of sports education. The guiding principles of the FTVS GEP are based on the 4Is framework developed within the SUPPORTER project:

- **Intersectionality:** The GEP addresses the combined impact of gender and other identity factors—such as age, ability, ethnicity, and socio-economic status—on students' and staff members' ability to engage in sports. By recognizing these intersecting dimensions, the GEP ensures that all individuals can participate in and benefit from sports

programs in an inclusive and equitable environment. Intersectionality is addressed through support for diverse groups of students and staff.

- **Innovation:** The plan promotes innovation in capacity-building by introducing creative and engaging learning methods tailored to the sports context. These include short educational videos, digital training modules, interactive formats, and case-based learning—tools designed to go beyond traditional lectures and foster a dynamic and inclusive learning environment. Regular updates of the curricula are part of the plan to gradually strengthen the integration of gender equality topics. This activity is innovative because it introduces new forms of training that have not been used at the faculty before.
- **Inclusiveness:** The development process was designed to be participatory and inclusive, actively involving academic and administrative staff, students, leadership, and equality representatives. By engaging the wider faculty community and external stakeholders, the plan ensures that diverse perspectives are valued and reflected in decision-making. Inclusivity is ensured through the active involvement of diverse groups in all activities.
- **Impact:** Each proposed measure is linked to specific objectives, indicators, and timelines, with clearly defined responsibilities to support effective implementation and long-term sustainability beyond the SUPPORTER project. The plan aims to achieve measurable progress in key areas such as leadership diversity, prevention of gender-based violence (GBV), and curriculum updates—delivering tangible benefits for both the faculty and the broader sports community. The impact is measured through specific indicators and regular evaluations.

By applying these principles, the GEP supports a more inclusive, safe, and equitable environment for all members of the FTVS UK community—both in academic life and in the broader world of sport.

4. Objectives of the FTVS GEP

4.1. Institutional Alignment and Active Engagement in University-Level Equality Structures

Objective: To ensure that the faculty-level Gender Equality Plan (GEP) aligns with the strategic goals and measures of the university-wide GEP and that FTVS UK is actively represented and engaged in the institutional structures advancing equal opportunities. This objective strengthens institutional

integration, accountability, and mutual learning, reflecting the principles of **impact** and **inclusiveness** through shared responsibility and ongoing collaboration.

Key Actions

- **Active Participation in the Equal Opportunities Council:** Ensure regular participation of a dedicated FTVS representative in the Charles University Equal Opportunities Council, with active contributions to agenda items and thematic working groups.
- **Implementation of University-Level GEP Measures at Faculty Level:** Systematically review and incorporate university-level GEP measures into faculty-level implementation cycles, including aligning timelines, communication strategies, and reporting tools.
- **Knowledge Transfer and Internal Communication:** Facilitate the internal dissemination of relevant outcomes, tools, and recommendations from the university-level GEP through briefings, internal newsletters, or working group updates.

Indicators

- Attendance and contribution of FTVS representative at Equal Opportunities Council meetings. Frequency of internal communication updates regarding university-wide GEP matters.
- Number and frequency of internal communication updates on university-wide equality issues (e.g., briefings, intranet posts, newsletters)
- Number of university-level measures adopted at the faculty level.

Timeline

- Regular reporting and alignment review: Starting Q3 2025; reviewed annually
- Communication tools (e.g., intranet updates); pilot version by Q3 2025

Responsibility: Dean's Board, FTVS UK Equality Representative, GEP Coordinator

4.2. Creating a Supportive and Health-Conscious Work-Life Environment

Objective: To support a healthy and sustainable balance between athletic, academic, and personal responsibilities by fostering a caring and inclusive organizational culture. This goal directly addresses the need for **wellbeing**

and **intersectional** realities, recognizing that both staff and students face specific stressors and varying challenges depending on their personal circumstances. The objective reflects the principles of **inclusiveness** and **impact**, aiming to create long-term structural support through responsive policies and services.

Key Actions

- **Flexible Scheduling and Return-to-Work Guidelines:** Offer tailored options for staff and students returning from parental leave or long-term caregiving, ensuring no disadvantage in career or academic progression. These guidelines promote flexible work arrangements that reflect diverse needs related to sport, caregiving, and personal wellbeing.
- **Awareness Campaigns:** Provide accessible and user-friendly information (e.g., brochures, intranet resources, social media, direct email or Teams communication, interviews) about existing support services for those balancing sports, work, and family. Organize thematic events and debates with respected figures from the world of sports and academia who advocate for gender equality, wellbeing and work-life integration.

Indicators

- Uptake of flexible scheduling arrangements by men and women. Qualitative feedback from returning staff and students.
- Gender distribution among students, faculty, and staff.

Timeline

- Guidelines to be piloted in Q2 2026.
- Annual review and updates starting in 2027.

Responsibility: FTVS UK Human Resources Department, Dean's Board, academic departments.

4.3. Advancing Gender Balance in Recruitment, Career Progression, and Leadership

Objective: To promote equitable representation, inclusive and intersectional practices in hiring, career development, and leadership appointments across all faculty levels. This objective directly responds to the need for **equal representation support**, while reflecting the principles of **intersectionality**, **inclusiveness**, and **impact** by addressing structural inequalities through measurable and sustainable action.

Key Actions

- **Equitable Representation in Committees:** Ensure gender and intersectional balanced representation on all hiring, promotion, and strategic planning committees, especially in areas related to education, research and faculty management. Attention will be paid not only to gender balance but also to other relevant dimensions of diversity—such as age, ethnicity, disability, and socio-economic background.
- **Leadership Workshops:** Organize dedicated workshops to support professional growth and leadership readiness among underrepresented groups. These workshops will include mentoring, practical training, and inspirational talks delivered by role models—advancing innovation in leadership development.

Indicators

- Proportion of individuals in academic and administrative decision-making positions disaggregated not only by gender, but also—where relevant and where data are available—by other diversity dimensions such as age, ethnicity, disability status, and socio-economic background.
- Raising awareness actions on the topic years needed for women and for men to make career advancements.
- Number of workshops. Number of participants. Numbers of training hours attended by women and men. Feedback from the participants of the workshops.

Timeline

- Internal HR procedure description by Q4 2025.
- First data report in Q2 2026; reviewed annually.

Responsibility: Dean's Board, FTVS UK Human Resources Department, sports department leadership.

4.4. Gender mainstreaming in Sports Curriculum and Research

Objective: To systematically embed gender perspectives into teaching, learning, and research across all sports-related disciplines, enhancing both academic quality and social relevance. This objective responds to the need for **equal representation support** and **education on solving social situations**. The key actions address **intersectionality** by encouraging the integration of diverse perspectives into teaching and research—particularly those related to gender in combination with age, ethnicity, disability, and

socio-economic background. It is **innovative** in its use of interactive and case-based learning formats tailored to the sports context, which go beyond traditional lectures. The objective promotes **inclusiveness** by involving a wide range of stakeholders in curriculum development and by ensuring that teaching materials reflect the diversity of the student and staff population.

Key Actions

- **Curriculum Revision:** Support course directors in revising syllabi to include content on gender bias, media representations of athletes, power structures in sports, and leadership diversity. Encourage the development of new interdisciplinary modules that reflect current research and practical realities.
- **Faculty Training:** Provide targeted training for academic staff to enhance their ability to integrate inclusive and intersectional (representing people of different age, ethnic, socio-economic background etc.) teaching materials and gender-sensitive approaches into coaching, sports science, and physical education courses. Trainings will include real-life case studies and interactive formats, reflecting innovative pedagogical practices.
- **Resource Sharing:** Promote the use of existing e-learning materials, short videos, and brochures on gender+ topics. Facilitate debates, peer exchange and access to innovative tools to support gender-inclusive teaching strategies.

Indicators

- Number of revised or newly developed syllabi with integrated gender content. List of the resources.
- Number of training hours (e.g. Gender related topics) attended by academic staff by man and woman. Feedback from attendees and analyses of the debates.
- Number of theses or research projects addressing gender-related topics.

Timeline

- Internal syllabi revision procedure description by Q4 2025.
- Testing of the targeted training Q2 2026; internal training procedure description Q3 2026.
- First data report in Q4 2026; reviewed annually.

Responsibility: Course instructors, Department of Internal Affairs, cooperating sports associations. Ombudspersons.

4.5. Gender-Based Violence (GBV) Prevention and Response

Objective: To establish a proactive framework for the prevention, early detection, and resolution of gender-based violence (GBV) within sports-specific settings. This directly addresses the need to manage power balance in hierarchical relationships such as coach–athlete dynamics and supports **wellbeing** and **social safety**. The objective reflects all four principles—**intersectionality**, **inclusiveness**, **innovation**, and **impact**—through inclusive training formats, awareness strategies, and sustainable reporting structures.

Key Actions

- **Mandatory Social Safety & GBV Training:** Expand current training modules to include real-life sports scenarios with a focus on GBV prevention, social safety, and ethical behaviour. Ensure all faculty and staff complete this training. This approach combines innovation and impact by integrating meaningful, context-specific learning. The training will incorporate intersectional scenarios that reflect diverse experiences based on gender, age, ethnicity, and disability. It is innovative in its use of real-life sports-based case studies and interactive formats, and inclusive by ensuring accessibility for all staff and students regardless of background or role.
- **Ombudsperson Coordination and Reporting Mechanisms:** Provide transparent and accessible reporting procedures that ensure confidentiality and protection against retaliation. Complement the process with awareness-raising short videos and discussions embedded into practical sports courses. The reporting mechanisms are designed to be inclusive and accessible, with attention to the needs of individuals from underrepresented or vulnerable groups. Intersectionality is addressed by ensuring that materials and support services reflect a range of lived experiences, and innovation is reflected in the integration of awareness-raising tools directly into sports practice settings.
- **Bystander Intervention Awareness:** Integrate bystander intervention strategies into coaching education, enabling both students and staff to respond constructively and promptly to incidents of harassment or misconduct. This action reinforces inclusiveness and individual empowerment. This action promotes inclusiveness by empowering all members of the faculty community to act against inappropriate behaviour, regardless of their position. It is intersectional in that it prepares individuals to recognize and respond

to situations involving overlapping vulnerabilities (e.g. gender and disability), and innovative through its integration into coaching education and practical training environments.

Indicators

- Training completion rates across faculty and staff by men and women. Participation rates in gender equality training programs.
- Awareness campaigns on the roles of the ombudspersons. Awareness levels of gender equality policies among staff and students.
- Satisfaction rate on incidents reported to ombudspersons (qualitative feedback from the persons, who were reporting, from the persons, who were involved and from the management).
- Raising awareness activities on wellbeing and social safety (e.g., number of viewership of educational videos)
- Number of participants in workshops or lessons focused on bystander intervention strategies.

Timeline

- 100% staff members attended Social Safety & GBV Training by and the procedure for the new staff Q4 2027.
- First data report in Q4 2026; reviewed annually.

Responsibility: FTVS UK Ombuds contact persons, Dean's Board, future teachers and future coaches.

5. Implementation Structure and Stakeholders

Dean's Board: Provides leadership endorsement, resource allocation, and overall accountability.

FTVS UK HR and Administration: Oversees training, data collection, and schedule coordination.

Academic Staff (Teachers, Researchers): Integrate updated curriculum modules, assist in implementing flexible scheduling, and support bystander intervention efforts.

Faculty contact persons: Serve as confidential contact points for students and staff, collecting qualitative feedback related to workplace climate, inclusion, and gender-related issues. They play a key role in identifying emerging challenges and escalating urgent matters for timely discussion by the Dean's Board or other relevant bodies.

Students and External Stakeholders: Engage in pilot trainings, provide feedback on campaign materials, and contribute real-world perspectives on sports-specific GBV risks.

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

The monitoring and evaluation (M&E) of the FTVS GEP are designed to ensure the effective implementation, continuous improvement, and long-term sustainability of gender equality measures. The M&E process builds on existing governance mechanisms and institutional practices at the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport, Charles University, and is aligned with the 4-Is framework (Intersectionality, Innovation, Inclusiveness, and Impact) developed within the SUPPORTER project.

6.1. Monitoring Process

Objective: To ensure timely tracking of the implementation status of GEP objectives and activities, and to identify potential challenges or gaps in delivery.

Structure and Activities:

- **Departmental Staff Meetings:** Departmental staff meetings are held regularly at FTVS UK and serve as an established forum for internal communication and coordination. If there is an issue to be raised, it will be first addressed during the departmental staff meeting. This ensures that matters arising at the departmental level—whether operational, academic, or staff-related—can be identified early and escalated appropriately. Once an issue is raised, it will be fully addressed at the Leadership Coordination Meeting.
- **Leadership Coordination Meetings:** The Leadership Coordination Meetings are held monthly. Department heads meet with the Dean's Board to review progress, share updates on faculty-specific activities, and address the issues raised during the departmental staff meetings. Reports from the meetings are officially recorded by administrative staff and made available on the website.
- **Student Evaluation Surveys:** We will work with the existing student evaluation surveys administered twice per academic year and update it to allow students to share feedback related to wellbeing and safety. We will ensure that by the 2026/2027 academic year, these topics are included. Collected results will be reviewed on an annual basis to inform ongoing monitoring and evaluation of the GEP.

- **Contact Persons Feedback Mechanism:** The two FTVS contact persons systematically collect and annually report on confidential feedback from students and staff regarding workplace climate, inclusion, and gender-related challenges. In cases where urgent or serious gender-related issues arise, they are promptly brought to the attention of the Dean's Board and included on the agenda for discussion and action.
- **Dedicated GEP Indicators Tracking Sheet:** Maintained by the Dean's Office and updated twice a year in collaboration with the HR department, this document records progress on implementation milestones, indicators, and participation metrics.
- **Dean's Board Meetings:** Monitor implementation progress and address any barriers or adjustments needed for GEP measures twice a year (tracking sheet). GEP-related issues are included on the agenda if urgent action is needed. The Dean's Board Meetings are held weekly.

6.2. Evaluation Process

Objective: To assess the outcomes, relevance, and impact of GEP actions against defined objectives, and to inform future policy development and planning cycles.

Structure and Activities:

- **Annual GEP Review in the Faculty's Year-End Report:** A dedicated section in the annual report will summarize GEP implementation, results, feedback, and next steps.
- **Targeted Questionnaire (once in 2 years):** Brief, anonymous questionnaires for each stakeholder group (students, staff, management) will assess perceptions of inclusiveness, use of support services, training relevance, and barriers to gender equality.
- **Focus Group / Thematic Discussion (once a year):** Optional, lightly facilitated focus group will explore selected topics such as GBV prevention, inclusive leadership, or flexible work culture.
- **Feedback from Contact Persons (once a year):** Collected data from ombuds officers will serve as a key qualitative input for evaluating the faculty's climate, effectiveness of intervention mechanisms, and systemic barriers.

Recommendations and Action Plan Updates:

- Evaluation findings will be discussed at the Dean's Board Meetings

- Monthly Leadership Coordination Meetings directly inform updates to GEP actions. Where gaps are identified, recommendations will be discussed at the leadership level and integrated into the upcoming implementation cycle.

Roles and Responsibilities

Stakeholder Group	Key Responsibilities
Dean's Board	Oversight and strategic guidance, twice a year review of implementation progress
HR and Dean's Office	Data management, indicator tracking, questionnaire administration
Department Heads	Operational follow-up, staff engagement, reporting on faculty-level progress
Contact Persons	Ongoing collection of qualitative feedback, participation in evaluation discussions
Students & Staff	Participation in surveys, focus groups, and feedback mechanisms

Timeline Summary

Activity Type	Frequency
GEP item monitoring (Dean's Board)	Twice a year
GEP tracking sheet update	Twice a year
Student evaluation survey	Twice a year
Targeted GEP questionnaires	Once in 2 years
Focus groups / discussions	Once a year
Annual report and strategic review	Once a year

7. Timeline Overview

This timeline summarizes the key actions and milestones for the implementation of the FTVS UK Gender Equality Plan 2025–2027. It aligns with the strategic objectives outlined in Chapter 4 and reflects the implementation and evaluation structure described in Chapter 6.

Action	Timeline	Responsibility
Formal approval of FTVS UK 4I-GEP	Q2 2025	Dean's Board, GEP Coordinator
Appointment of FTVS representative to Charles University Equal Opportunities Council	Q3 2025	Dean's Board
Internal procedure for equitable committee composition	Q4 2025	HR Department, Dean's Board
Description of internal syllabus revision procedure	Q4 2025	Course Instructors, Department of Internal Affairs
Launch of leadership workshops and mentoring programme	Q1 2026	HR Department, Sports Department Leadership
Pilot testing of faculty training on gender-sensitive teaching	Q2 2026	Course Instructors, Department of Internal Affairs
Systematic implementation of flexible return-to-work guidelines	Q2 2026	HR Department
Launch of Social Safety & GBV training for current staff	Q2 2026	Ombuds Contact Persons, HR Department
Introduction of gender + curriculum updates	Q4 2026	Course Instructors

Action	Timeline	Responsibility
Launch of internal communication tools for knowledge transfer from university GEP	Q4 2026	GEP Coordinator, Equality Representative
Launch of awareness campaigns and thematic events on wellbeing and inclusion	Annually, starting Q4 2026	Dean's Board, HR, Communications Team
Annual GEP implementation review in year-end faculty report	Starting Q1 2026	Dean's Board, GEP Coordinator
Biannual GEP tracking sheet updates	Starting Q1 2026	HR Department, Dean's Office
Institutional student evaluation surveys with questions related to wellbeing and safety	Twice annually, starting Q1 2026	Academic Affairs, GEP Coordinator
Targeted GEP stakeholder questionnaires	Every 2 years (first in Q2 2026)	Dean's Office, HR
Annual focus group / thematic discussions	Starting Q3 2026	GEP Coordinator, Ombuds Officers
Annual feedback from contact persons	Starting Q4 2026	GEP Coordinator, Ombuds Officers
Integrate bystander intervention strategies into coaching education and practical training	Starting Q4 2026	Academic Affairs, Dean's Board
100% completion of Social Safety & GBV training for current staff	Q4 2027	Ombuds Contact Persons, HR Department

8. Conclusion

The FTVS UK Gender Equality Plan (4I-GEP) for 2025–2027 represents a significant step toward creating a fair, inclusive, and high-performing

academic and sports environment. Building on the institutional framework of Charles University and enriched through international collaboration—particularly the SUPPORTER project—this plan translates strategic commitments into context-specific actions tailored to the realities of sport education.

The GEP is structured around four guiding principles: **Intersectionality**, **Innovation**, **Inclusiveness**, and **Impact**. These principles are embedded across all objectives, ensuring that gender equality is addressed not only through policy declarations but through measurable actions, targeted interventions, and institutional learning.

The five strategic objectives outlined in Chapter 4 address key areas of concern:

- fostering a supportive and health-conscious work–life environment,
- promoting gender balance in recruitment and leadership,
- embedding gender perspectives into teaching and research,
- strengthening prevention and response mechanisms to gender-based violence (GBV), and
- aligning faculty efforts with university-wide structures and strategies.

By doing so, FTVS UK affirms its role as both a contributor to and a beneficiary of the broader equality agenda at Charles University. Regular participation in the university’s Equal Opportunities Council and the implementation of university-level GEP measures at the faculty level will further reinforce coherence and shared accountability.

The implementation and evaluation mechanisms described in Chapter 6 ensure that progress is monitored, challenges are identified early, and actions are continuously improved. A structured timeline (Chapter 7) sets clear expectations for implementation phases and responsibility-sharing across leadership, HR, academic staff, and student stakeholders.

In embracing gender equality as both a value and a strategic necessity, FTVS UK commits to building a safer, more diverse, and empowering academic and sporting environment for all. Through sustained collaboration, evidence-based action, and an inclusive culture, this plan sets the foundation for long-term positive change—within the faculty and beyond.